

Article

Comparative Long-Term Monitoring of Microplastics in the Effluent of Three Different Wastewater Treatment Plants with Two, Three, and Four Treatment Stages

Michael Toni Sturm¹, Daphne Argyropoulou², Erika Myers¹

¹ Wasser 3.0 GmbH, Neufeldstr. 17a-19a, 76187 Karlsruhe, Germany

² Sanitary Engineering Laboratory, Department of Water Resources and Environmental Engineering, School of Civil Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, 15780 Athens, Greece

* Correspondence: schuhen@wasserdreinull.de; Tel.: +49-721-15-65-95-93

Abstract: Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are important point sources for microplastics (MPs) in the environment. For effective mitigation measures and regulations, it is important to monitor their release into the environment and understand the level of MPs in the WWTP effluents based on different treatment technologies. In this study, we compare the MP levels in the effluents of three different municipal WWTPs which each use a different treatment concept: a conventional three-stage WWTP, one with an additional fourth cleaning stage using powdered activated carbon, and a two-stage WWTP utilizing a membrane bioreactor (MBR). Long-term monitoring was performed on the WWTP effluents using the same standardized methods for sample collection, preparation, and detection, based on fluorescent staining. Despite the various advanced treatment processes, there are no significant differences in the resulting MP contamination in the investigation of WWTP effluents. The average MP concentrations in the effluents were 21.8 MPs/L for the conventional three-stage WWTP, 15.1 MPs/L for the four-stage WWTP, and 15.1 MPs/L for the MBR. Further, the MP contamination in all effluents shows a strong fluctuation over time. These findings highlight the need for standard MP monitoring at WWTPs, to gain a better understanding of the MP emission in different treatment processes. Further, it highlights the need for a fourth treatment stage that specifically targets MP removal to effectively prevent the MP release from WWTPs into the environment.

Keywords: microplastics; wastewater treatment; WWTP; microplastic detection; microplastic analysis; microplastic analytics; fluorescent dyes; long-term monitoring

Academic Editors: Chengtao Li and Xueqiang Lu

Received: 6 February 2025

Revised: 24 February 2025

Accepted: 26 February 2025

Published: 28 February 2025

Citation: Sturm, M.T.; Argyropoulou, D.; Myers, E.; Korzin, A.; Ronsse, P.; Zernikel, O.; Schober, D.; Schuhen, K. Comparative Long-Term Monitoring of Microplastics in the Effluent of Three Different Wastewater Treatment Plants with Two, Three, and Four Treatment Stages. *Water* **2025**, *17*, 711. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w17050711>

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Microplastics (MPs), defined as plastic particles less than 5 mm in diameter, have emerged as a significant environmental pollutant, posing risks to aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems [1]. Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are critical nodes in the pathway of MPs from urban environments to natural water bodies [2,3]. Despite the high MP removal efficiency in WWTPs, due to the high volumes of treated wastewater, substantial quantities still escape into the environment, raising concerns about their ecological and health impacts (Figure 1) [1,4]. MP can be ingested by a wide range of organisms, leading to physical harm, disturbance of cell functions and potential release or bioaccumulation of toxic substances [1]. For humans, MP have been found in various tissues and are linked to

potential health risks, including immunotoxicity and endocrine disruption, although more research is needed to fully understand their long-term impacts [5].

Figure 1. Overview of the pathway of MP exposure from WWTPs to human, animal, and environment and subsequent negative impacts [1,5].

Recent studies have highlighted the prevalence of MPs in wastewater effluents and sludge. For instance, a meta-analysis by Azizi et al. (2022) revealed removal efficiencies of conventional three-stage treatment plants ranging from 64% to over 99%, depending on the study [6]. A 2024 review by Miino et al. discusses the MP removal between the first, second, and third cleaning stages, as well as for a polishing treatment (e.g., filtrate membrane disc filter, disinfection by UV, ozone, or chlorination), with the majority of MPs being removed during the primary treatment [7]. However, long-term studies providing absolute numbers obtained from comparable sampling methods are not available.

The remaining MPs, particularly those smaller than 150 μm , are often discharged into aquatic systems or accumulate in sewage sludge, which is frequently applied to agricultural lands [8].

The fate and transport of MPs in WWTPs are influenced by various factors, including the physical and chemical properties of the plastics, the design and operational parameters of the treatment processes, and the environmental conditions. Jose et al. (2024) reviewed the transformation and fate of MPs in WWTPs, emphasizing the need for standardized methodologies to accurately assess their removal and environmental release [9].

The recent revision of the EU Urban Wastewater Directive (UWWTD) introduces several key measures to address MPs [10]. The updated directive is a first step towards the systematic monitoring of MPs in wastewater treatment plants, although the current proposal is not sufficient for obtaining representative data on the actual MP concentrations [11]. Additionally, the directive aligns with the EU's zero-pollution action plan, aiming to prevent harmful substances, including MPs, from being released into the environment. This revision also emphasizes the "polluter pays" principle, requiring industries responsible for MP pollution to bear the costs of advanced treatment processes. These changes reflect a significant step towards mitigating the environmental impact of MPs and enhancing the overall effectiveness of wastewater treatment in Europe.

In the UWWTD, it is stated that WWTPs serving populations greater than 150,000 PE (population equivalent) must conduct MP sampling at least twice annually, ensuring no more than six months between samples [10]. Additionally, WWTPs with capacities exceeding 150,000 PE must monitor MPs in sewage sludge. In contrast, plants serving over

10,000 PE are required to sample only once every two years and are not required to monitor the sludge. A standardized methodology for monitoring and detection must be established within 30 months of the directive's enactment. Once approved by the EU Parliament, this methodology must be incorporated into national legislation.

Monitoring MPs involves three main steps: sampling, sample preparation, and detection [12]. Currently, there are no standardized methods for these steps, leading to variations in methodologies across different studies, which complicates result comparisons [13]. Additionally, detecting MPs is often labor-intensive and expensive due to the intricate sampling and preparation processes, as well as the costly detection methods that require long processing times, resulting in low sample throughput [14]. The fluorescence staining method used in this study, in combination with the standardized sampling and sample preparation protocols, offers a quick, comparable, and user-friendly alternative [15,16].

The focus of this study is the comparison of three municipal wastewater with two, three, and four stages regarding their MP emissions, applying the same sampling, sample preparation, and detection method. Compared are a conventional three-cleaning-stage WWTP in Germany, a four-stage WWTP in Germany that uses powdered activated carbon (PAC) and cloth filtration, and a two-stage WWTP in Greece, using a membrane bioreactor (MBR). MBRs and cloth filtration are often discussed in the scientific literature as efficient methods for MP removal in WWTP [17]. This comparison should clarify if the WWTPs show significant differences in their MP emissions or if additional treatment steps are necessary.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Demo Site Descriptions

The following three WWTPs were selected because they use different treatment technologies, which are compared in terms of their MP release. WWTP-A is a conventional three-stage municipal WWTP, while WWTP-B is a conventional WWTP with an additional fourth treatment stage using PAC and cloth filtration. WWTP-C has 2 cleaning stages, including a modern MBR. MBRs and cloth filtration are often discussed in science as solutions for the MP emission from WWTPs into the environment, which is why these WWTPs are particularly interesting for this investigation [17].

2.1.1. WWTP-A: Conventional 3-Stage WWTP

WWTP-A is a municipal WWTP with a capacity of 80,000 population equivalents (PE). The WWTP receives wastewater from approximately 51,000 people, along with wastewater from industrial and commercial enterprises, two hospitals, and agriculture—primary viticulture. An overview of the WWTP can be seen in Figure 2. The WWTP runs three treatment stages with a cleaning performance of 95–97% for COD:

1. A primary treatment using rakes, a sand trap, and a fat separator;
2. Secondary biological treatment (nitrification and denitrification);
3. Chemical treatment: tertiary phosphate elimination.

The flow rate ranges from 9000 to 13,000 m³/d during dry weather periods and up to 40,000 m³/d during rain events. The average hydraulic retention time (HRT) is 24 h, and the average sludge retention time is 12–14 d. The treated wastewater in the effluent has an average chemical oxygen demand (COD) of 20 mg/L, 6.5 mg/L nitrate, <1 mg/L ammonia, and a total phosphorus concentration of 0.3 mg/L.

Figure 2. Image and flow diagram of WWTP-A, with conventional 3-stage treatment.

2.1.2. WWTP-B: Conventional WWTP with Additional 4th Cleaning Stage

The municipal WWTP-B is a 4-stage WWTP equipped with primary treatment using rakes, a sand trap, and a fat separator, a secondary biological treatment (nitrification and denitrification), and a tertiary phosphate elimination. For the fourth treatment stage, a powdered activated carbon (PAC) treatment is used, followed by a cloth filter for separation of the PAC and TSS reduction (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Image and flow diagram of WWTP-B, with 4 treatment stages.

When WW volumes are too high, e.g., during rain events, the capacity of the 4th cleaning stage is exceeded, and a bypass discharges the treated water after the 3rd cleaning stage directly into the receiving water.

The catchment area consists of residential and industrial areas and accounts for 250,000 PE. The dry weather inflow ranges from 30,000 m³/d to 65,000 m³/d; the max. rainwater inflow is 135,000 m³/d. The average sludge retention time is 9 d. The treated effluent has an average CSB of 12 mg/L and the following concentrations: nitrate

11 mg/L, ammonia < 0.1 mg/L, nitrite < 0.1 mg/L, and a total phosphorus concentration of 0.2 mg/L.

2.1.3. WWTP-C: 2 Treatment Stages, with a Membrane Bioreactor

WWTP-C (Figure 4) has been constructed on three distinct elevation levels. The administrative buildings and the pretreatment units are located at the highest level, while the biological treatment units are located on the second and third levels. The chlorination unit is downstream at the end of the field and receives the treated wastewater by gravity. The plant consists of two main lines that receive the same influent and operate in parallel:

1. A conventional activated sludge system with a capacity of 8400 m³/d;
2. A membrane bioreactor with a capacity of 10,800 m³/d.

Figure 4. Image and flow diagram of WWTP-C, with two parallel treatment lines: a two-stage conventional treatment and a two-stage treatment with an MBR.

In total, the WWTP has been designed to facilitate the needs of 48,000 PE. The influent wastewater in this system originates from two main sources: municipal wastewater collected through the sewer network of Mykonos and wastewater from septic tanks. Seasonal tourism has a strong influence on wastewater volumes, as in the off-season, the population can decline to under 10,000 PE.

To ensure effective treatment, both streams initially pass through bar screening and grit removal to eliminate large debris and sand.

After preliminary treatment, the combined wastewater stream is directed into two parallel treatment lines for further processes, i.e., biological treatment and disinfection (an overview of the WWTP processes is shown in Figure 4). It is noted that at the time of the samplings, the final filtration step (before chlorination) was not used by WWTP due to maintenance. The treated wastewater shows an average BOD₅ of 15 mg/L, COD of 3, nitrate concentration of 10 mg/L, and total phosphorus of 5 mg/L.

2.2. Microplastic Monitoring

The MP monitoring follows a standard protocol using standardized sample collection by filtration, sample processing by hydrogen peroxide digestion, and MP detection by fluorescent staining and imaging [15,18,19]. The effectiveness of the method was evaluated using MPs and natural particles to determine recovery rates and risks for false positives [15,18]. The advantage of this method is the fast and cost-effective application, which makes it efficient to process high numbers of samples [20]. The disadvantages are missing chemical characterization of polymer types and the risks of false positives with natural particles [20].

2.2.1. Sample Collection

Sampling in the WWTP effluents followed Sturm et al. (2023) [15]. Samples were taken in duplicates using the Wasser 3.0 Particle Sampling Unit (PSU, Wasser 3.0 gGmbH, Karlsruhe, Germany) [11].

The PSU combined a 10 µm filter cartridge with a pump, tubing, valves, and a water meter for direct and easy on-site application [15]. The water was pumped from the inlet through the filter cartridge with a pressure of max. 4 bar. The filter retained all particles larger than 10 µm, including MPs. The materials used are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Materials used for the construction of the Wasser 3.0 PSU.

Part	Model No.	Supplier
Rotary Pump	MG80B C-B-CMS1B	Grundfos, Erkrath, Germany
Filter cartridge (10 µm)	01WTGD	Wolftechnik Filtersysteme GmbH & Co., KG, Weil, Germany
Water meter	Zenner ETKD	ZENNER International GmbH & Co. KG, Saarbrücken, Germany
Tubing	TUFLON-PTFE/NW25	Industriebedarf Castan GmbH, Freiberg, Germany

The inlet and outlet tubes were connected to the PSU. The inlet tube needed to be placed before the outlet tube in the flow direction to prevent the inflow of prefiltered water. The inlet tube was made from black PVC, which was not detected by the fluorescent staining method and avoided contamination of the samples. Additionally, a 2 mm suction basket was applied to avoid clogging or damaging the pump.

For each sample, 100 L of treated wastewater was run through the filter. Subsequently, the filter cartridge was removed, and the filtered solids were flushed into a 2.5 L glass bottle using a spray bottle filled with tap water. The 2.5 L glass bottle was used for sample storage and transport.

2.2.2. Sample Processing

Sample processing was conducted using a hydrogen peroxide treatment followed by fluorescence staining [18]. Hydrogen peroxide treatment reduces the number of natural particles by chemical decomposition while MPs are not degraded and remain in the samples [13,21]. For samples from WWTP-C, the sampling preparation protocol was successfully transferred and implemented, with pretreatment being conducted in Greece and the remaining treatment and analysis conducted in Germany.

First, 500 mL subsamples were filtered over a 10 µm stainless steel filter disc (Wolftechnik Filtersysteme GmbH & Co., KG, Weil, Germany) using vacuum filtration (DURAN® Filtering Apparatus, Cat. No. 257106304, DWK Life Sciences GmbH, Mainz, Germany). The filter disc and retained solids were placed into a beaker, which was filled with 20 mL hydrogen peroxide (35%, AB171423, abcr GmbH, Karlsruhe, Germany) and 3–5 grains of iron(II)sulfate (AB203817, abcr GmbH, Karlsruhe, Germany). Subsequently, the beaker was placed on the heating plate and kept at 100 °C for 1 h. After cooling down for 10 min, the

filter disc was removed from the beaker and rinsed with water into the same beaker. The filter disc was inserted again in the vacuum filtration, and the whole sample was filtered. The filter disc was removed, and all solids were flushed from the filter disc into the empty beaker.

In the next step, the fluorescence dye abcr eco Wasser 3.0 detect mix MP-1 (AB930015, abcr GmbH, Karlsruhe, Germany) was added to the beaker. The fluorescent dye was developed to selectively stain MP, but not natural particles and residues [15,18,22]. In total, 25 µL of the fluorescent dye was added to the sample ($c = 0.25$ mg/L) and kept for 1 h at 80 °C. After staining, the sample was filtered through a black filter membrane (Metricel® Black PES Membranfilter, 0.80 µm, Pall, Dreieich, Germany) and stored in a Petri dish.

2.2.3. Detection

Fluorescent imaging was performed using a Zeiss Axiozoom.V16 (Carl Zeiss Microscopy Deutschland GmbH, Oberkochen, Germany). The microscope was equipped with a PlanNeoFluar Z 1.0× Objective and an Axiocam 712 mono. For green fluorescence, a custom-made filter set from AHF Analystechnik AG (Tübingen, Germany) was used.

The images were taken with the following parameters (Table 2).

Table 2. Parameters for fluorescence imaging of MP samples.

Parameter	Setting
Exposure	20 ms
Aperture	100%
Binning	3.3
Bit depth	14 Bit
Zoom	10
Total magnification (ocular)	100
Scaling (per Pixel)	1.035×1.035 µm
Depth of field	8.9 µm
Excitation	430–480 nm
Emission	500–570 nm
Beam splitter	495 nm
Image processing	Stitching

For analysis, five 3.9×3.8 mm squares of the 47 mm round filter were photographed and analyzed. For image analysis, the particle counting module for the software ZEN 3.8 (Carl Zeiss Microscopy Deutschland GmbH, Oberkochen, Germany) was used. The particle counting module (ZEN Toolkit 2D, Carl Zeiss Microscopy Deutschland GmbH, Oberkochen, Germany) can automatically detect MPs based on brightness threshold values.

2.2.4. Contamination Control

For contamination control, all samples were handled in a separate laboratory that was used only for MP analytics. The laboratory was cleaned before each use with a lint-free cleaning rag, and lint-free clothing was worn (4510 M, 3 M Deutschland GmbH, Ness, Germany). Before entering the laboratory, the lint-free suit was rinsed using a lint roller with adhesive paper. Additionally, an air filter was operated, glass laboratory equipment was used if possible, and the samples were always covered with aluminum foil. Further, regular blanks were measured and subtracted from the detected MP concentrations.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Comparison of the WWTPs

The MP contamination of the three WWTPs is compared in Figure 5 and Table 3. In total, 84 samples were taken at WWTP-A, 13 at WWTP-B, and 41 at WWTP-C.

Figure 5. Boxplot of the MP contamination of the effluents of the three different WWTPs. Note: For each day, the mean of the duplicate-sample takes was calculated and counted as one sample. For WWTP-A, two outliers (432 MPs/L and 391.8 MPs/L) are not displayed.

Table 3. Summarized key indicators of the MP monitoring in the three different WWTPs. Note: For each day, the mean of the duplicate-sample takes was calculated and counted as one sample.

	WWTP-A 3rd CS	WWTP-B 3rd CS	WWTP-B 4th CS	WWTP-C MBR
No. of samples	84	13	13	41
Mean [MPs/L]	21.8	36.2	15.1	15.1
S.D. [MPs/L]	62.6	30.1	14.7	11.4
Median [MPs/L]	7.9	25.3	13.0	13.6
Min [MPs/L]	0.0	7.7	0.8	1.0
Max [MPs/L]	432.4	105.1	58.7	61.2

The data show the MP contamination at all WWTPs, with the final effluents showing a similar MP concentration range and fluctuations. No statistically significant difference was detected in the final effluents (Welch's *t*-test, two-sided, unpaired, WWTP-A–WWTP-B: $t(79) = 0.83$, $p = 0.41$; WWTP-A–WWTP-C: $t(94) = 0.95$, $p = 0.34$; WWTP-B–WWTP-C: $t(17) = -0.01$, $p = 0.99$). It is notable that the relatively small sample size at WWTP-B affects the robustness of the *t*-test, which means that smaller differences between the MP contamination levels might not be recognized [23].

At all WWTPs, fragments were almost exclusively detected (compare Figure 6). In comparable studies at WWTPs, fibers released from synthetic textiles and fragments are typically the dominant morphologies of the MPs found [24]. The reasons for this could be the absence of textile fibers in the investigated WW or the relatively aggressive chemical hydrogen peroxide digestion which may decompose the fibers [25]. However, this pretreatment is necessary, as fluorescence staining as a detection method is more prone to false positives by natural particles [19]. Therefore, the number of MPs in the form of fibers might be underestimated.

Figure 6. Example images of processed MP samples from the three WWTPs. Shown in the photos are green fluorescence and marked in red are particles detected as MPs from the detection software. Note: The sample from the WWTP-B 4th CS contains residues from the PAC, which are visible as black particles in the color photo.

The effluent of the third CS at WWTP-B shows an elevated MP contamination with a mean of 36.2 MPs/L, compared to 15.1 MPs/L in the fourth CS effluent of WWTP-B. At WWTP-C, the MBR effluent had a mean of 15.1 MPs/L. These differences are statically significant (Welch's t-test, two-sided, unpaired, WWTP-B third CS–WWTP-B fourth CS:

$t(12) = 3.55$, $p = 0.04$, WWTP-B third CS–WWTP-C MBR effluent: $t(40) = 8.39$; $p = 0.03$). The difference between the third CS at WWTP-B and the third CS at WWTP-A is also statistically significant (Welch's t-test, two-sided, $t(83) = 3.18$, $p = 0.002$).

At WWTP-B, there was an average reduction of $36.9 \pm 56.7\%$ from the effluent of the third CS to the effluent of the fourth CS. Despite the application of a fourth CS (PAC) and cloth filtration, the WWTP-B MP release is similar to that of WWTP-A with three conventional CSs. An investigation of MP removal by applying cloth filtration at the WWTP in Oldenburg in Germany by Mintenig et al. (2017) showed an MP reduction of 97% [26]. A laboratory study by Sembring et al. (2021) showed an MP removal efficiency of 34–85%, depending on the MP size and the pore size of the used cloth filter [27]. The cloth filter applied at WWTP-B has a pore size of 5 μm . Whether MPs larger than 5 μm can still pass through is unclear and requires further investigation. One possibility could be operational issues.

The MBR at WWTP-C does not show a lower MP contamination compared to WWTP-A or WWTP-B. Bayo et al. (2022) investigated the effectiveness of MP removal of an MBR in a Spanish WWTP (EDAR Águilas) and found a removal efficiency of 79% [28]. In contrast, a study by Egea-Corbacho et al. (2023) at the Søholt WWTP in Denmark found the MBR to effectively remove 99.69% of MPs [29]. As the MP influent concentration of the MBR was not measured, the removal efficiency cannot be specified. It is unclear if the MP emission is caused by high influent concentrations or unintentional release during MBR operation. To clarify the reason for MPs passing the MBR, further investigations would be needed.

Looking at the measured fluctuation in MP concentrations and the respective standard deviation (S.D.), minimum, and maximum values, the WWTP-A shows the highest range of MP levels (Table 3). The highest MP level of 432.4 MPs/L and lowest MP concentration of 0 MPs/L were both measured at WWTP-A. As fewer samples were taken at the other WWTPs, extremely high values which occur more rarely might not have been captured during the investigation. After the fourth CS in WWTP-B, the detected MP contamination ranged from 0.8 to 58.7 MPs/L, and after the MBR at WWTP-C, the values ranged from 1 to 61.2 MPs/L. These fluctuations were also found in other studies of MPs in WWTPs and highlight the importance of regular MP monitoring in WWTPs to obtain an adequate evaluation of the MP contamination and discharges [6,11,30]. Without a sufficiently high number of samples, it is not possible to make a qualified statement about the level of MP contamination, as those rarely occurring high levels of contamination are not captured.

For all WWTPs, the median is lower than the mean. The mean is more affected by the higher values which occur more rarely. A few very high values can significantly increase the mean while having little influence on the median.

Correlations with rainfall events and inflow volumes were not observed; it is still unclear what causes these strong fluctuations in MPs in WW. External influences, such as MP emission levels into the WW and the heterogeneous distribution of MPs in the water, are potential causes [31]. These events can occur randomly and therefore cause strong variances in the MP levels. For example, a study investigating the daily fluctuations of MPs in a Chinese WWTP found that influent concentrations fluctuated between 29 MPs/L and 46,178 MPs/L within a 24 h period [32].

The results obtained from other studies that investigated MP emissions in WWTPs show that the MP contamination found in the WWTP effluents varies greatly among studies and is strongly influenced by the monitoring method used [6]. A meta-analysis comparing 407 studies of MPs in WWTPs found MP contaminations of 0.002–7863 MPs/L after the second CS and 0.003–447 MPs/L after the third CS. The averages among the studies were 5.62 MPs/L after the second CS and 1.97 MPs/L after the third CS. Comparing these results to the MP levels obtained in this study, it is found that the MP concentrations detected

in this study are in the higher range. A reason for this could be the minimum detectable particle size of 10 μm within this study, which is relatively small. The smaller the minimum detectable particles are, the higher the concentrations found [33]. This underlines the need for comparable and standardized MP detection.

3.2. Extrapolation of the MP Discharge

The MP concentrations measured can be used to extrapolate the yearly discharge and the discharge per population equivalent (PE) (Table 4). The estimation is based on the measured average MP concentrations, the yearly WW discharges, and the PE of the WWTPs. It is notable that the WWTP-B uses a bypass of the fourth CS for rain events with high flow volumes. In such cases, the treated wastewater exceeds the capacity of the fourth CS and is directly discharged into the receiving waters. As the MP concentrations after the third CS are higher than after the fourth CS, this also increases the number of MPs released. In 2024, the WW release was 15.9 million m^3/year for the fourth CS and 3.5 million m^3/year for the third CS (over the bypass).

Table 4. Extrapolated amounts of MP discharged per year.

WWTP	WWTP-A 3rd CS	WWTP-B 3rd + 4th CS	WWTP-C MBR	WWTP-C Conventional
WW discharge [m^3/year]	5,000,000	19,400,000 *	1,700,000	600,000
PE	80,000	250,000	35,500 **	12,500 **
WW discharge [m^3/PE and year]	63	78	47	47
MPs/year	109,246,918,081	367,721,607,927	25,014,447,030	n.a.
MPs/PE and year	1,365,586	1,470,886	704,632	n.a.

Notes: * Representing 15.9 million m^3/year 4th CS, 3.5 million m^3/year 3rd CS over bypass; ** total of 48.000 PE, divided in relation to the amount of wastewater in each line.

The discharge volumes of WW range from 1.7 million m^3/year in the WWTP-C MBR line to 19.4 million m^3/year in WWTP-B, which is more than 11 times more. These volumes of WW correspond to an extrapolation of the MP emissions, ranging from 25 billion MPs/year for the WWTP-C MBR line to 367 billion MPs/year for WWTP-B. These differences are mainly due to the different yearly WW discharge volumes, as the concentrations in the effluents are similar.

It is notable that WWTP-A and WWTP-B reach close values for MPs/PE and year with 1.36 million MPs/PE and year for WWTP-A and 1.47 MPs/PE and year for WWTP-B. WWTP-C has a lower discharge of 0.7 million MPs/PE and year. This might be also due to the lowest WW discharge per PE and year for WWTP-C with 47 m^3/year and PE. The lower amount of WW per year and PE is caused by the seasonal population fluctuations, which drop below 10,000 PE in the off-season, and due to the lower precipitation and higher water scarcity attributed to the climate conditions.

Dronjak et al. (2024) estimated an emission of 51 billion MPs/year for a much larger WWTP in Barcelona, Spain, with 358,000 PE and a design flow of 43,000 m^3/day [34]. This results in a release of 142.458 MPs/PE and year, which is comparably lower than the results of the current study. However, the varying methodologies used make a proper comparison of results difficult.

A variety of methods for reducing MPs in sewage treatment plant effluents are being investigated and discussed [7]. It is important to highlight that in addition to households, other emitters like industry or road runoff can strongly affect the MP entries into the WW [35]. Thus, methods of upstream prevention of MP inputs into the WW, such as removal at plastic producing or processing industries, MP reduction and removal in laundering processes, or pretreatment of road runoff would be useful starting points [36–38].

The advantages of upstream prevention are reduced costs, as less WW needs to be treated, the polluter pays for the MP removal, and the sludge does not become contaminated with MPs, as the MPs retained in the sludge may then be transferred to soils if it is applied as fertilizer [3,36].

This study confirms WWTPs as important point sources for MPs in the environment, as they cannot completely remove MPs from the WW. This leads to MP emissions into the environment and elevated local contamination in the WWTP effluent, posing a risk to ecosystems [39]. Also, treatment methods such as MBRs and cloth filtration do not effectively prevent MP emissions.

4. Conclusions

The results of monitoring the MP levels in the effluents of three different WWTPs show that there is no significant difference in the MP concentrations released. Neither the application of an MBR nor the use of a fourth treatment stage with PAC and cloth filtration shows a reduced MP release in the effluent compared to a conventional three-stage WWTP. As cloth filtration and MBR are often discussed as solutions for MP removal in WWTPs, more studies are needed to evaluate the effectiveness of these methods.

For scientifically sound statements, comparable methods for sampling, sample processing, and MP detection are particularly necessary. Also, appropriate sampling intervals and sample sizes are necessary, as MP concentrations in wastewater are subject to constant and large fluctuations.

Furthermore, the results illustrate that wastewater treatment plants with an MBR and a fourth CS are also significant point sources of MPs in the environment and that high amounts of MPs are still released into the environment due to the high wastewater volumes. This highlights that there is an ongoing need for research into targeted MP removal solutions to reduce MP emissions from WWTPs beyond the standard fourth cleaning stages.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, M.T.S., E.M., D.S. and K.S.; methodology, M.T.S., D.S. and K.S.; validation, M.T.S. and K.S.; formal analysis, M.T.S., E.M. and K.S.; investigation, P.R., D.A., O.Z., M.T.S., A.K. and D.S.; resources, K.S.; data curation, M.T.S., P.R., A.K. and K.S.; writing—original draft preparation, M.T.S., E.M. and K.S.; writing—review and editing, M.T.S., E.M. and K.S.; visualization, M.T.S. and E.M.; supervision, K.S.; project administration, K.S.; funding acquisition, K.S. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This project has received co-funding from the European Union's HORIZON EUROPE innovation program under grant agreements 101093964 and 101112877. This publication reflects the views only of the author, and the European Commission cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. This project has also received part of its funding from the Veolia Foundation (Germany) | Project konti | detect.

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in this study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Acknowledgments: The authors thank abcr GmbH, Karlsruhe, Germany, Entsorgungs- und Wirtschaftsbetriebe Landau (EWL, Germany), Eigenbetrieb Stadtentwässerung Pforzheim (Germany), in particular Christian Wahlandt und Andrea Gloß, and the WWTP Mykonos (Greece) for the project-related support. Further, we thank Eleftheriou G. Antonios (MCG, Greece) for the sampling of the WWTP Mykonos.

Conflicts of Interest: Michael Toni Sturm, Erika Myers, Anika Korzin, Pieter Ronsse, Oleg Zernikel, Dennis Schober and Katrin Schuhen (authors) were employed by the non-profit organization Wasser 3.0 gGmbH). The remaining authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

References

1. Galloway, T.S.; Cole, M.; Lewis, C. Interactions of microplastic debris throughout the marine ecosystem. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.* **2017**, *1*, 116. [CrossRef]
2. Browne, M.A.; Crump, P.; Niven, S.J.; Teuten, E.; Tonkin, A.; Galloway, T.; Thompson, R. Accumulation of microplastic on shorelines worldwide: Sources and sinks. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2011**, *45*, 9175–9179. [CrossRef]
3. Parashar, N.; Hait, S. Recent advances on microplastics pollution and removal from wastewater systems: A critical review. *J. Environ. Manag.* **2023**, *340*, 118014. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
4. Zhao, B.; Rehati, P.; Yang, Z.; Cai, Z.; Guo, C.; Li, Y. The potential toxicity of microplastics on human health. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2024**, *912*, 168946. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
5. Ezhava, S.R.; Lobo, V.H.; Rodge, S.P. Hazards of microplastics on human health and its mitigation strategies. *Toxicol. Environ. Health Sci.* **2025**, *17*, 1–14. [CrossRef]
6. Azizi, N.; Nasserri, S.; Nodehi, R.N.; Jaafarzadeh, N.; Pirsahab, M. Evaluation of conventional wastewater treatment plants efficiency to remove microplastics in terms of abundance, size, shape, and type: A systematic review and Meta-analysis. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* **2022**, *177*, 113462. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
7. Carnevale Miino, M.; Galafassi, S.; Zullo, R.; Torretta, V.; Rada, E.C. Microplastics removal in wastewater treatment plants: A review of the different approaches to limit their release in the environment. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2024**, *930*, 172675. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
8. Iyare, P.U.; Ouki, S.K.; Bond, T. Microplastics removal in wastewater treatment plants: A critical review. *Environ. Sci. Water Res. Technol.* **2020**, *6*, 2664–2675. [CrossRef]
9. Jose, S.; Lonappan, L.; Cabana, H. Prevalence of microplastics and fate in wastewater treatment plants: A review. *Env. Chem Lett* **2024**, *22*, 657–690. [CrossRef]
10. European Parliament. Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council Concerning Urban Wastewater Treatment (Recast). Available online: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-7108-2024-INIT/en/pdf> (accessed on 16 April 2024).
11. Sturm, M.T.; Myers, E.; Korzin, A.; Schober, D.; Schuhen, K. Long-Term Monitoring of Microplastics in a German Municipal Wastewater Treatment Plant. *Microplastics* **2024**, *3*, 492–502. [CrossRef]
12. Mahapatra, S.; Maity, J.P.; Singha, S.; Mishra, T.; Dey, G.; Chandra Samal, A.; Banerjee, P.; Biswas, C.; Chattopadhyay, S.; Patra, R.R.; et al. Microplastics and nanoplastics in environment: Sampling, characterization and analytical methods. *Groundw. Sustain. Dev.* **2024**, *26*, 101267. [CrossRef]
13. Prata, J.C.; Da Costa, J.P.; Duarte, A.C.; Rocha-Santos, T. Methods for sampling and detection of microplastics in water and sediment: A critical review. *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.* **2019**, *110*, 150–159. [CrossRef]
14. Singh, B.; Kumar, A. Advances in microplastics detection: A comprehensive review of methodologies and their effectiveness. *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.* **2024**, *170*, 117440. [CrossRef]
15. Sturm, M.T.; Myers, E.; Korzin, A.; Polierer, S.; Schober, D.; Schuhen, K. Fast Forward: Optimized Sample Preparation and Fluorescent Staining for Microplastic Detection. *Microplastics* **2023**, *2*, 334–349. [CrossRef]
16. Ho, D.; Liu, S.; Wei, H.; Karthikeyan, K.G. The glowing potential of Nile red for microplastics Identification: Science and mechanism of fluorescence staining. *Microchem. J.* **2024**, *197*, 109708. [CrossRef]
17. Talvitie, J.; Mikola, A.; Koistinen, A.; Setälä, O. Solutions to microplastic pollution—Removal of microplastics from wastewater effluent with advanced wastewater treatment technologies. *Water Res.* **2017**, *123*, 401–407. [CrossRef]
18. Sturm, M.T.; Myers, E.; Schober, D.; Korzin, A.; Schuhen, K. Development of an Inexpensive and Comparable Microplastic Detection Method Using Fluorescent Staining with Novel Nile Red Derivatives. *Analytica* **2023**, *4*, 27–44. [CrossRef]
19. Sturm, M.T.; Horn, H.; Schuhen, K. The potential of fluorescent dyes-comparative study of Nile red and three derivatives for the detection of microplastics. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* **2021**, *413*, 1059–1071. [CrossRef]
20. Shruti, V.C.; Pérez-Guevara, F.; Roy, P.D.; Kutralam-Muniasamy, G. Analyzing microplastics with Nile Red: Emerging trends, challenges, and prospects. *J. Hazard. Mater.* **2022**, *423*, 127171. [CrossRef] [PubMed]
21. Gulizia, A.M.; Brodie, E.; Daumuller, R.; Bloom, S.B.; Corbett, T.; Santana, M.M.F.; Motti, C.A.; Vamvounis, G. Evaluating the Effect of Chemical Digestion Treatments on Polystyrene Microplastics: Recommended Updates to Chemical Digestion Protocols. *Macro Chem. Phys.* **2022**, *223*, 2100485. [CrossRef]
22. Sturm, M.T.; Myers, E.; Schober, D.; Korzin, A.; Thege, C.; Schuhen, K. Comparison of AOP, GAC, and Novel Organosilane-Based Process for the Removal of Microplastics at a Municipal Wastewater Treatment Plant. *Water* **2023**, *15*, 1164. [CrossRef]
23. Ahad, N.A.; Yahaya, S.S.S. The selection criteria in determining the robustness of t-test. In Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Mathematical Sciences, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, 17–19 December 2013; AIP Publishing LLC: New York, NY, USA, 2014; pp. 1112–1117.

24. Cristaldi, A.; Fiore, M.; Zuccarello, P.; Oliveri Conti, G.; Grasso, A.; Nicolosi, I.; Copat, C.; Ferrante, M. Efficiency of Wastewater Treatment Plants (WWTPs) for Microplastic Removal: A Systematic Review. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* **2020**, *17*, 8014. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
25. Vojnović, B.; Mihovilović, P.; Dimitrov, N. Approaches for Sampling and Sample Preparation for Microplastic Analysis in Laundry Effluents. *Sustainability* **2024**, *16*, 3401. [[CrossRef](#)]
26. Mintenig, S.M.; Int-Veen, I.; Löder, M.G.J.; Primpke, S.; Gerdt, G. Identification of microplastic in effluents of waste water treatment plants using focal plane array-based micro-Fourier-transform infrared imaging. *Water Res.* **2017**, *108*, 365–372. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
27. Sembiring, E.; Mahapati, W.O.S.W.; Hidayat, S. Microplastics particle size affects cloth filter performance. *J. Water Process Eng.* **2021**, *42*, 102166. [[CrossRef](#)]
28. Bayo, J.; López-Castellanos, J.; Olmos, S. Membrane bioreactor and rapid sand filtration for the removal of microplastics in an urban wastewater treatment plant. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* **2020**, *156*, 111211. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
29. Egea-Corbacho, A.; Martín-García, A.P.; Franco, A.A.; Quiroga, J.M.; Andreasen, R.R.; Jørgensen, M.K.; Christensen, M.L. Occurrence, identification and removal of microplastics in a wastewater treatment plant compared to an advanced MBR technology: Full-scale pilot plant. *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* **2023**, *11*, 109644. [[CrossRef](#)]
30. Blair, R.M.; Waldron, S.; Gauchotte-Lindsay, C. Average daily flow of microplastics through a tertiary wastewater treatment plant over a ten-month period. *Water Res.* **2019**, *163*, 114909. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
31. Barkmann-Metaj, L.; Weber, F.; Bitter, H.; Wolff, S.; Lackner, S.; Kerpen, J.; Engelhart, M. Quantification of microplastics in wastewater systems of German industrial parks and their wastewater treatment plants. *Sci. Total Environ.* **2023**, *881*, 163349. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
32. Shan, W.; Li, B.; Zhang, H.; Zhang, Z.; Wang, Y.; Gao, Z.; Li, J. Distribution, characteristics and daily fluctuations of microplastics throughout wastewater treatment plants with mixed domestic—Industrial influents in Wuxi City, China. *Front. Environ. Sci. Eng.* **2022**, *16*, 1–9. [[CrossRef](#)]
33. Baruah, A.; Sharma, A.; Sharma, S.; Nagraik, R. An insight into different microplastic detection methods. *Int. J. Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2022**, *19*, 5721–5730. [[CrossRef](#)]
34. Dronjak, L.; Exposito, N.; Rovira, J.; Florencio, K.; Emiliano, P.; Corzo, B.; Schuhmacher, M.; Valero, F.; Sierra, J. Screening of microplastics in water and sludge lines of a drinking water treatment plant in Catalonia, Spain. *Water Res.* **2022**, *225*, 119185. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
35. Nafea, T.H.; Al-Maliki, A.J.; Al-Tameemi, I.M. Sources, fate, effects, and analysis of microplastic in wastewater treatment plants: A review. *Environ. Eng. Res.* **2024**, *29*, 230040. [[CrossRef](#)]
36. Bergmann, M.; Arp, H.P.H.; Carney Almroth, B.; Cowger, W.; Eriksen, M.; Dey, T.; Gündoğdu, S.; Helm, R.R.; Krieger, A.; Syberg, K.; et al. Moving from symptom management to upstream plastics prevention: The fallacy of plastic cleanup technology. *One Earth* **2023**, *6*, 1439–1442. [[CrossRef](#)]
37. Venghaus, D.; Neupert, J.W.; Barjenbruch, M. Evaluation of a Modular Filter Concept to Reduce Microplastics and Other Solids from Urban Stormwater Runoff. *Water* **2023**, *15*, 506. [[CrossRef](#)]
38. Periyasamy, A.P. Environmentally Friendly Approach to the Reduction of Microplastics during Domestic Washing: Prospects for Machine Vision in Microplastics Reduction. *Toxics* **2023**, *11*, 575. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
39. Altuğ, H.; Erdoğan, Ş. Wastewater Treatment Plants as a Point Source of Plastic Pollution. *Water Air Soil Pollut.* **2022**, *233*, 1–14. [[CrossRef](#)]

Disclaimer/Publisher’s Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.